

of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) gave a yellow solid which upon crystallisation from a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–benzene (5:1) furnished yellow needles, m.p. 162–65°, $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ ($[M^+]$ at m/z 288); λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 250 (4.50), 315 (4.20) and 360 nm (3.75); ν_{max} (KBr) 3380br (bonded OH), 1660, 1625, 1605 and 1570 cm^{-1} (chelated α, β -unsaturated C=O), suggesting the presence of xanthone skeleton in **1**. The 1H nmr spectrum (90 MHz; $CDCl_3$) of the compound showed four *meta*-coupled doublets for four aromatic protons at δ 6.30 (1H, d, J 3 Hz), 6.60 (1H, d, J 3 Hz), 6.90 (1H, d, J 3 Hz) and 7.45 (1H, d, J 3 Hz) besides two singlets of three protons each at δ 3.70 and 3.85 due to two methoxyl groups. On complete methylation with $(CH_3)_2SO_4$, the xanthone (**1**) yielded a dimethyl derivative (**2**), m.p. 226°, $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ ($[M^+]$ at m/z 316). Thus **1** must be a dihydroxydimethoxyxanthone. The appearance of four aromatic proton signals as four different *meta*-coupled doublets is suggestive of the fact that four oxygen functions (two methoxyl and two hydroxyl) are distributed in both the rings and are located in 1,3-positions; of these, the low field aromatic proton signal at δ 7.45 is consistent with a proton at C-8 having an oxygen substituent at C-7³, hence two oxygen functions in ring-B are at C-5 and C-7 positions. The presence of chelated hydroxyl necessitates the location of one of the hydroxyls at C-1. The parent xanthone was found to be insoluble in 5% Na_2CO_3 solution and its uv spectrum remains unaffected by addition of sodium acetate solution. This suggests that one of the methoxyl groups present in the compound must be at C-3⁴. Further, the second methoxyl group was assumed to be at C-5 as in the 1H nmr spectrum of the diacetate (**3**), C-8 proton signal is shifted downfield to δ 7.75 suggesting the presence of free OH group at C-7⁶. Thus, the new xanthone was characterised as 1,7-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyxanthone (**1**). Finally, identity of the dimethyl derivative (**2**) as 1,3,5,7-tetramethoxyxanthone from comparison of physical constants and spectral data conclusively settles the above view.

- 1**; R = H
2; R = Me
3; R = Ac

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Lipid Constituents from *Artemisia annua*†

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ARTEMISIA annua (Compositae) is a Chinese medicinal plant. It has been introduced in India where it is growing successfully at CIMAP Regional Centre, Srinagar¹. During a large scale isolation of artemisinin, a promising antimalarial drug², it was also of interest to examine the other compounds. This has resulted in the isolation of four compounds, A, B, C and D.

The air-dried powdered leaves and stems of *A. annua* (50 kg) were extracted with n-hexane (6 × 180 dm³) and the resulting extract was concentrated to a syrup (1.1 kg). A portion of it (25 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (750 g), eluting with n-hexane with an increasing proportion of EtOAc in hexane. The fractions (200 ml each) were collected and monitored by tlc. Compound A (35 mg) was eluted in hexane, compound B (110 mg) in hexane–EtOAc (9:1), compound C (70 mg) in hexane–EtOAc (17:3) and compound D (40 mg) in hexane–EtOAc (19:1).

Compound A, m.p. 68°; ν_{max} 2960, 2920, 2855, 730, 720 (long chain), 1380, 1370 and 1180 cm^{-1} (isopropyl group)³; M^+ at m/z 450 corresponding to its molecular formula as $C_{32}H_{66}$. The generation of ions at m/z 435 ($[M-Me]^+$) and 420 ($[M-2Me]^+$) together with the ratio of abundances of $[M-Me]^+$ / $[M]^+$ indicated the compound to be branched having two methyl groups as substituents⁴. A close look at the mass spectrum of compound A indicated that the

Fig 1 Mass fragmentation pattern of compounds 1 and 3.

intensity of C_nH_{2n+1} peaks, after a maximum at $n=4$ steadily declined upto $n=28$ followed by a strong peak at $n=29$ (m/z 407). The strong ion peak at $n=29$ [$M-43$] $^+$ suggested the attachment of the methyl group at C-2 b . The evidence obtained so far along with the presence of a twelve proton doublet in the 1H nmr spectrum indicated that the chain was

terminated at both ends by isopropyl groups. Thus, compound A could be characterised as 2,29-dimethyltriacontane (1).

Compound B, m.p. 82° , ν_{max} 2940, 2850, 720 (long chain), 1740 (ester C=O) and 1380 cm^{-1} showed in its 1H nmr spectrum two triplets (J 6 Hz) at δ 4.16 and 2.35 for the methylene protons of $-CH_2-O-CO-$ and $CH_2-CO-O-$ moieties, respectively, suggesting it to be a long chain saturated ester. This compound on alkaline hydrolysis furnished an alcohol, m.p. 88° , identified as hentriacontanol (m.m.p., co-tlc, MS), and an acid, m.p. 94° , identified as triacontanoic acid (MS and co-tlc). This compound, therefore, was characterised as hentriacontanyl triacontanoate (2).

Compound C, m.p. 86° , ν_{max} 3400 (OH), 1730 (CO), 2905, 2850, 730, 720 (long chain) and 1380 , 1370 , 1180 cm^{-1} (isopropyl group). The molecular weight of the compound ($C_{24}H_{48}O_2$) was indicated by the M^+ at m/z 368. The presence of an ion at m/z 353 [$M-Me$] $^+$ and the other ions at m/z 325 and 43 showed the presence of isopropyl group at one end of this compound whereas the loss of water to give an ion at m/z 350 [$M-H_2O$] $^+$ and the ion at m/z 337 [$M-CH_2OH$] $^+$ showed the presence of a $-CH_2OH$ group at the other end of the chain. The location of the carbonyl group at C-8 was established by the abundant α -fission ions at m/z 255, 227, 141 and 113 followed by characteristic β -fission ions, involving McLafferty rearrangement at m/z 270, 212, 156 and 98 e .

The double rearrangement ion characteristic for a ketone having γ -H in both the alkyl fragments was seen at m/z 58 e . The structure of compound C as 2-methyltricosan-8-one-23-ol (3) was also supported by its 1H nmr spectrum showing resonances for isopropyl group (δ 0.92, d), hydroxy methylene (δ 3.62, t) and two methylenes adjacent to carbonyl group (δ 2.25, t).

Compound D was identified as nonacosanol. It is interesting to note that Compositae is a good source of branched long chain constituents. They were reported earlier from *Echinops niveus* 7 .

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Tetramethylene Thiram Disulphide (Thiram) by Extraction of its Molybdenum Complex

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THIRAM sulphides are conveniently determined on the basis of the decomposition of this type of compounds by hot mineral acid to the amine and carbon disulphide. The amount of either of these hydrolysis products can be determined either iodometrically¹ or colorimetrically^{2,3}. Thiram mono- and disulphides may be determined if a digestion with sodium bisulphide is employed prior to the distillation from acid solution of the carbon disulphide⁴. Thiram could be titrated with copper sulphate in presence of hydroquinone⁵. Thiram is determined in grains by colorimetric method by cuprous chloride⁶. But these are all time-consuming processes. It is considered of interest to determine thiram by a simple, direct and rapid spectrophotometric method.

Accordingly, we present here a sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of thiram after extracting its molybdenum complex into isobutyl methyl ketone.

Experimental

A Spectronic 20 colorimeter was used for recording absorption measurements. Purity of thiram (Wilson Laboratories) was checked by elemental analysis and m.p. A 0.1% solution of thiram was prepared in 0.1N NaOH solution and boiled for 20 min, cooled, filtered and standardised³ and further diluted as desired with distilled water. A 2% (w/v) sodium molybdate (pure, E. Merck) solution was prepared in distilled water. Stock solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water or NaOH solution. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 400 μg of thiram was added 2M H_2SO_4 (0.5 ml) and 2% sodium molybdate (1.5 ml) and the final volume was made to 5 ml with distilled water. The aqueous solution was shaken with isobutyl methyl ketone (5 ml) for 1 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the organic phase was transferred into a dry tube containing anhydrous calcium chloride. Extract with

another 5 ml of isobutyl methyl ketone from the aqueous phase gave negligible absorbance indicating the complete extraction in the first step itself. A portion of the dried solution (first step) was taken and its absorbance was measured at 420 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of thiram-molybdenum complex in isobutyl methyl ketone was recorded against reagent blank. The complex absorbed strongly at 420 nm. The absorbance of the extract increased with the addition of upto 0.5 ml of 2M H_2SO_4 , but decreased with further addition. The absorbance of the extract remained constant for 1.0–2.0 ml of 2% sodium molybdate solution. Of all the solvents studied, this complex is not extractable into benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, toluene and hexane, but is extracted with n-butyl acetate, amyl acetate, diethyl ether, butan-2-one, ethyl acetate, acetyl acetate, isobutyl alcohol and isobutyl methyl ketone. Maximum absorbance was observed with isobutyl methyl ketone and hence used in this method. The absorbance of the complex remained practically constant for more than 2 h indicating that the complex is quite stable in the extract.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 5.0–110.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the final solution. The limit of detection is 1.2 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity (for an absorbance of 0.001) were calculated to be $0.156 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.154 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively at 420 nm. Aliquot containing 400 μg of thiram gave mean absorbance of 0.52 with ten replicate readings with relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.515\%$. In Cullen⁸ and Chmiel³ methods, minimum amount of thiram equivalent to 20 μg of CS_2 can be estimated, whereas in the present method, the minimum amount corresponds to 15.72 μg of CS_2 . Although this method is less sensitive than that of Lowen⁷, the minimum amount in this method corresponds to 10 μg of CS_2 , but is preferred because of its selectivity and its application in simultaneous determinations.

The composition of the molybdenum-thiram complex was found to be 1 : 1 i.e. $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2$ (TMTD).

Effect of diverse ions: Sample solutions containing 400 μg of thiram and various amounts of different alkali metal salts or metal ions were prepared and the determination of thiram was studied and the general procedure was applied. The following metal ions (μg amount in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of thiram 400 μg in 5 ml of the final solution: Pb^{II} (504), Bi^{III} (200), Zn^{II} (660), Cd^{II} (84) and Mn^{II} (40). Cu^{II} interfered strongly. But the following ions (mg amount in parenthesis) were tolerated: citrate (20), bromide (40), nitrate (1), chloride (1), oxalate (20), iodide (1), tartarate (10), thiosulphate (0.5), thiocyanate (0.5), EDTA (0.6), sulphide (0.5) and sulphite (0.6). Sodium orthophosphate interfered strongly.